

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MODELING OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (DCFRTTP) now regarded as the potential substitutes for metallic materials applied in mass-production automotive to mitigate global fossil consumption and ease the problem of air pollution. Many approaches have been developed to estimate the mechanical properties of short fiber composites. Currently, the mean field method like Mori-Tanaka model presents one of the most efficient and accurate approaches for the prediction of the composite mechanical properties, but some researches mentioned the limitation of Mori-Tanaka method that only DCFRTTP with low volume fraction and low aspect ratio are suitable for the simulation. In present study, the tensile properties of two kinds of DCFRTTP named CMT (carbon fiber mats reinforced thermoplastics) and UT-CTT (ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics) were analysed experimentally and analytically, the components and structural properties were measured in detail. The comparison between the Mori-Tanaka analytical and experimental results show difference with the previous studies. In UT-CTT with high volume fraction and high aspect ratio, good agreement was observed between the results of experiments and Mori-Tanaka model. On the other hand, in CMT with large range aspect ratio distribution and low volume fraction, mismatch was observed. The reason of this phenomenon was discussed and considered to be the fiber elastic deformation occurred during the impregnation process.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) showing outstanding suitability for lightweight applications and have being applied to automotive manufacturing industry in recent years. The outstanding molding and recycling properties combine with the advantages in less hazardous chemical emission manufacture processes of CFRTP insure the application to the mass-production vehicles to mitigate global fossil consumption and ease the pressure of air pollution [1]. Discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (DCFRTTP) is considered as the favorable composite for applications on mass-production vehicles because of the relatively high achievability for high cycle molding and complex-shaped molding, but the safety still play as the biggest obstacle to achieve the goal. Because the features of DCFRTTP like irregularity in the meso-level structure and molding process sensitivity make it difficult to give precise description of the mechanical properties.

The mechanical properties studies have been conducted in these decades. Different approaches have been tried to give accurate and effective estimation. Fu et al. calculated the tensile modulus and strength of DCFRTTP in different fiber aspect ratio and orientation based on the modified rule of mixtures [2, 3]. Piggott et al. managed to verify the accuracy of shear-lag model for the simulation of mechanical performance of short fiber reinforced plastics [4]. An accurate multi-scale FE (finite element) model was been established by Hashimoto et al. to conduct simulation of tensile strength of discontinuous carbon fiber/polypropylene composite with fiber orientation distribution [5]. And a comparison between the analytical and numerical homogenization methods was conducted by using a complex multi-scale FE model compare with the one step Mori-Tanaka model, two-step Self-Consistent/Voigt model and Lielens (Li)/Voigt model [6]. To date, the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method combined with a Mori-Tanaka type model presents one of the most efficient and accurate approaches for the prediction of

composite stiffness [7-9]. But the previous researches indicated the limitation in the volume fraction and orientation distribution of the inclusions of this method [6, 10]. However, none of them have studied the reason that lead to this consequence in detail.

In the present research, to analyse the mismatch of Mori-Tanaka model, two different DCFRTP with the structural properties beyond the apply limitation of Mori-Tanaka model declared in previous studies were prepared. The tensile experiments and structural properties analysis were conducted. Detail information of the components and structural properties were measured and put into the Mori-Tanaka model to compare with the experimental results.

2 MATERIALS AND PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

Two kinds of DCFRTP with different molding processes and structure features are introduced in this study (Fig. 1). Both of these two materials are considered to be the potential substrates for mass-production vehicles.

Figure 1: Appearance of CMT (Left) and UT-CTT (right).

One is CMT (carbon fiber mats reinforced thermoplastics), which is composed of PP (polypropylene) and CF papers (randomly oriented carbon fiber monofilaments). CMT is the typical mat structure composite that shows very good in-plane isotropy appearance, and is suitable for making complex shape parts. But the carbon fiber volume fraction (V_f) of CMT is restricted below 35% because the paper-like structure needs an enormous molding pressure to reach the required impregnation condition in high V_f [11], hence this material is not appropriate for applications in main stressed parts of the vehicles. In this paper, two CMT named CMT 1 and CMT 2 are applied, the difference between these two CMT is the V_f .

The other material is UT-CTT (ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics), which is composed of randomly oriented ultra-thin unidirectional prepreg tapes. The tape is manufactured with carbon fiber (TR 50S, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., LTD.) and Polyamid-6 (PA6), and the thickness of this tape is relatively thin (40 μm to 50 μm) compare with the conventional one (about 100 μm or more), and that is the reason we called this tape materials as ‘UT (ultra-thin)’. The composites molded by this ultra-thin tape show superiorities in suppress microcracking, delamination and splitting damage for static, fatigue and impact loadings compare with the conventional tape [12]. The tape is cut into different tape lengths: 12mm, 18mm, 24mm and 30mm. Through random distribution and compression molding processes, the UT-CTT materials are made. This material shows good in-plane isotropy, and because the fibers were impregnated before material molding, the UT-CTT have good flowability and suitable for complex shape molding. Additionally, the V_f of this material can reach over 50%, hence this material is presumed to be applied to the critical members of vehicle.

The CMTs are provided by TORAY Industries, Inc, and the UT-CTTs are provided by the Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture.

2.2 Experiments

Tensile experiments were conducted for both CMT and UT-CTT materials. Three specimens were prepared for each CMT; four specimens were prepared for all the UT-CTTs in different tape length. The tensile load is loaded to the specimens till the total fracture occurred and the strain of materials were measured by the extensometer.

Beside the DCFRTP, the tensile experiments of the matrices were also conducted to obtain the detail elastoplastic performances needed for the simulation. The tensile specimens were manufactured by the corresponding resins used in the CMT (PP) and UT-CTT (PA6) under injection molding processes. Because the fracture strain of these resins are much higher (higher than 30%) than the fracture strain of the CF (about 2%) and the composites (less than 2%), to ensure the measurement accuracy, only 5% strain of the matrices were recorded by the extensometer. The stress-strain curves of the matrices is fitted based on the J_2 -plasticity model which is given by:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{C} : \epsilon^e & J_2(\sigma) \leq \sigma_Y \\ \sigma_Y + kp + R_\infty [1 - e^{-mp}] & J_2(\sigma) > \sigma_Y \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $J_2(\sigma)$ is the von Mises equivalent stress. The σ_{eq} and σ_Y denote the equivalent Cauchy stress and the yield stress, respectively. ϵ^e is the elastic strain. \mathbf{C} is the Hooke's operator. The k , R_∞ and m denote the linear hardening modulus, hardening modulus and hardening exponent, respectively. The p is the accumulated plastic strain and expressed as:

$$p = \int \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} d\epsilon_{ij}^p d\epsilon_{ij}^p \quad (2)$$

The J_2 -plasticity model curve is plotted using the experimental data, and the parameters used in the fitting J_2 -plasticity curves are applied to the simulation processes.

2.3 Structural analysis

After the mechanical properties of the materials were collected in the tensile tests, other physical properties that are needed for the simulation were also measured.

The V_f of both the CMTs and UT-CTTs were calculated by ash test. The ash test is used to determine the real V_f of the composites by measuring material densities and the weight differences before and after burn off the resin.

The aspect ratio of the reinforcement of the CMTs and UT-CTTs were also determined. For CMT materials, because the reinforcements are the randomly oriented carbon fiber monofilaments, so the aspect ratio can be simply calculated by the equation:

$$K_{CMT} = \frac{l}{d} \quad (3)$$

where K_{CMT} is the aspect ratio of reinforcement in CMT materials, l is the fiber length and d is the fiber diameter. The fiber length distribution was counted under microscope, and 1000 fibers were counted for each CMT.

On the other hand, because the reinforcement in UT-CTTs is not fiber but the prepreg tape, the aspect ratio of 3D structure tape is difficult to be described by the basic definition. Hence the definition of 3D aspect ratio generally used in the FEM (finite element methods) [13] is adopt in this study to calculate the aspect ratio of UT-CTTs. Therefore, the equivalent aspect ratio of the tape is calculated by this equation:

$$K_{CTT} = \frac{h_{max}}{2\sqrt{6}r_{max}} \quad (4)$$

where K_{CTT} is the equivalent aspect ratio of reinforcement in UT-CTT materials, r_{max} is the largest in-radius of the tetrahedrons that contained in the tape structure and h_{max} is the largest edge length of the

corresponding tetrahedron. Consequently, the aspect ratio of the tape structure in this study can be calculated by:

$$K_{CTT} = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2} * (ab + a\sqrt{b^2 + c^2} + b\sqrt{c^2 + a^2} + \sqrt{a^2b^2 + b^2c^2 + c^2a^2})}{2\sqrt{6}abc} \quad (5)$$

where a is the tape length, b is the tape width and c is the tape thickness.

Also the CMT and UT-CTT structures were analysed using the 3D X-ray scanner. The scanned images were input to the image processing software, after the binarization and modelling processes, the fiber structural models were built. Based on structure analysis, the fiber orientation information is calculated. The state of orientation of a fiber can be characterized from the angles ϕ and θ as defined in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Definition of the in-plane angle ϕ , the out-of-plane angle θ and the fiber orientation unit vector \mathbf{p} .

The average fiber orientation of the materials are calculated by the 3D fiber orientation tensor [14]:

$$\mathbf{O} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta & \sin \phi \cos \phi \sin^2 \theta & \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \sin \phi \cos \phi \sin^2 \theta & \sin^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta & \sin \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta & \cos^2 \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where the \mathbf{O} denote the fiber orientation. The angles ϕ and θ are the average angles of the materials and calculated by the structure analysing software.

The V_f , aspect ratio and fiber orientation obtained in these analyses are also applied to the simulation processes.

2.4 Mean field modelling

Mean field methods are considered to be the effective analytical homogenization approach to analyse the mechanical properties of DCFRTP. In this study, the Mori-Tanaka model [15], which is commonly used for discontinuous randomly oriented fiber reinforced composites, was adopted to conduct the simulation. Benveniste presented the Mori-Tanaka formulation to describe composites with randomly oriented inclusions [8]:

$$\mathbf{E}^{MT} = \mathbf{E}_m + V_f \{ (\mathbf{E}_f - \mathbf{E}_m) : \mathbf{T} \} : [V_m \mathbf{I} + V_f \{ \mathbf{T} \}]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{E} denote the stiffness tensor, subscripts m and f represent the matrix and fiber, respectively. The curly bracket $\{ \cdot \}$ stand for orientation averaging. Tensor \mathbf{T} is given by:

$$\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}_m : \mathbf{E}_m^{-1} : (\mathbf{E}_f - \mathbf{E}_m)]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{S}_m is Eshelby's tensor where the matrix is the infinite media [7].

Because only tensile strength is considered in this study, the component failures are considered as the failure indicators of the fibers and matrices during the simulation:

$$f_d = \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{c} \quad (9)$$

where the c is the corresponding strength of the stress direction of σ_{ij} .

Because the matrices is homogeneous, so the axial tensile strength (X), in-plane tensile strength (Y) and transverse shear strength (S) are regarded as same value. While, the strength of the matrices is difficult to determine because the fracture strain of the resins are much higher than the fibers and composites. So, the equivalent matrices strength σ_m^* is determined as the mean tensile stress in the matrix at the fiber breaking strain [4]. Otherwise, the carbon fiber is regarded as anisotropic material, the Y and S are considered to be $\frac{1}{4}$ of the X , averagely [16]. Additionally, when the strength under complex stress condition is studied, failure criterion like Tsai-Hill and Tsai-Wu [17, 18] will be taken into consideration.

The mean field modelling software Digimat-MF is used in this study to conduct the calculation processes.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Components and structural properties

The carbon fibers used in this study were the commercialized general carbon fibers, and the mechanical properties are listed following the catalogue data (Table 1).

After the resins tensile tests, the stress-strain curves were fitted by the J_2 -plasticity curves, and the fitting results are illustrated in Fig. 3. The results show very good agreement between the experimental and calculation curves, and the parameters used in the fitting J_2 -plasticity curves are listed in Table 2.

The V_f of CMTs and UT-CTTs calculated by the ash test are presented in Table 3. As introduced before, the main difference CMT 1 and CMT 2 is the V_f , while the V_f of UT-CTT are almost the same.

The aspect ratio distribution of CMT 1 and CMT 2 are shown in Fig. 4. The results indicated the difference between the CMT in different V_f : when the V_f is higher, the probability of short fiber (in relative low aspect ratio) increased in the materials.

Besides, the equivalent aspect ratio of the UT-CTTs were calculated based on Equation (5), and the results are listed in Table 4.

	Young's Modulus E (GPa)	Tensile Strength σ (MPa)	Fracture Strain ε_f (%)	Diameter d (μm)	Density ρ (g/cm^3)
T700	230	4900	2.1	7	1.80
TR50	240	4900	2.0	7	1.82

Table 1: Properties of carbon fibers.

	Density (g/cm^3)	Young's Modulus E (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio ν	Yield Stress σ_Y (MPa)	Hardening Modulus R_∞ (MPa)	Hardening Exponent m	Linear Hardening Modulus k (MPa)
PP	0.90	2.10	0.35	9.2	24	135	100
PA6	1.14	3.31	0.40	15.0	56	350	160

Table 2: Properties of the matrices.

	CMT 1	CMT 2	UT-CTT 12	UT-CTT 18	UT-CTT 24	UT-CTT 30
V_f (%)	11.1	19.4	52.2	55.1	52.8	53.1

Table 3: Fiber volume fraction of materials.

Figure 3: Comparison of the experimental and calculation fitting stress-strain curves of the matrices PP (a) and PA6 (b).

Figure 4: Aspect ratio distribution of CMT 1 (a) and CMT 2 (b).

	UT-CTT 12	UT-CTT 18	UT-CTT 24	UT-CTT 30
Tape length (mm)	12	18	24	30
Tape width (mm)			5	
Tape thickness (mm)			0.05	
Aspect ratio (K)	212.3	305.1	400.0	496.7

Table 4: Tape size and aspect ratio of UT-CTT.

The material structural models were scanned and built as illustrated in Fig. 5. Then the fiber orientation of in-plane direction and out-of-plane direction were calculated and presented in Fig. 6. The fiber models show the apparently difference between CMT and UT-CTT. The UT-CTT show much higher fiber density, and the fiber structure is more like locally independent laminate. On the other hand, the CMT model represented the typical mat-structure composite. The fiber orientation models also support this observation. Both the CMT and UT-CTT are consisted by the randomly oriented fibers, but it is very clear from the Fig. 6 (b) that the UT-CTT have visible lamination structure, while the CMT is composed by the randomly oriented carbon fibers (Fig. 6 (a)). In contrast, the out-of-plane fiber orientation of CMT and UT-CTT have insignificant difference that both the fibers are rarely oriented through out-of-plane direction. Additionally, the average fiber orientation tensor of CMT and UT-CTT were calculated. Analogy with the structure models that the in-plane and out-of-plane fiber orientation between CMT and UT-CTT have no apparent difference, the orientation tensors also almost same:

$$\mathbf{O}_{CMT} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.490 & 0.004 & 0.001 \\ 0.004 & 0.490 & 0.001 \\ 0.001 & 0.001 & 0.020 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{O}_{UT-CTT} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.491 & 0.005 & 0.002 \\ 0.005 & 0.491 & 0.002 \\ 0.002 & 0.002 & 0.018 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Because both the in-plane fiber orientation show sufficient statistically accuracy, the in-plane direction components are calculated to be in same value.

Figure 5: Structure models of CMT (a) and UT-CTT (b).

Figure 6: In-plane fiber orientation of CMT (a) and UT-CTT (b); out-of-plane fiber orientation of CMT (c) and UT-CTT (d).

Finally, the failure indicators of the fibers and matrices introduced before were calculated based on the catalogue and experimental data. The results are listed in Table 5.

	T700	TR50	PP (σ_m^*)	PA6 (σ_m^*)
X_t (MPa)	4900	4900	26	55

Table 5: Failure indicator of each components.

3.2 Results comparison

Using the components and structural properties data measured in this study, the Mori-Tanaka model based simulation is conducted. The comparison between the experimental and simulation results of the Young's modulus and tensile strength are summarized, respectively (Figs. 7 and 8).

Figure 7: Young's modulus results of CMT (a) and UT-CTT (b) from experiments and simulations.

Figure 8: Tensile strength results of CMT (a) and UT-CTT (b) from experiments and simulations.

The results of stiffness simulation show very good agreement (averagely 4% difference) in UT-CTT materials in all the tape length. While in CMT, the simulation results generally higher than the experimental value and this difference increase with the increase of V_f (8% higher in CMT 1 and 20% in CMT 2). In the comparison of strength, analogy results are observed. The good agreement are shown in UT-CTT that the simulation results have averagely 5% difference compare with the experimental results in all the tape length; and in contrast, the simulation results of the CMT show apparently higher value than the experimental one (13% higher in CMT 1 and 31% in CMT 2).

The stress-strain curves till the fracture are also presented for both the CMT materials (Fig. 9) and UT-CTT materials (Fig. 10) of the simulations and the experiments. Different from the Young's modulus and tensile strength results, both the simulation curves of CMT and CTT show considerable agreement of the fracture strain with the experimental one except the CMT 1 that the fracture strain of

simulation is relatively low. The main different point between the CMT and UT-CTT curves is that both the simulation and experimental curves of UT-CTT show good linearity, while in CMT materials, the experimental curves display plastic yielding progression before the final failure but the simulation curves are totally linear till the fracture occurred.

Figure 9: Stress-strain curves of CMT, the solid lines *_1/2/3 are experiment data and the double dot dash lines *_S are simulation results.

Figure 10: Stress-strain curves of UT-CTT, the solid lines *_1/2/3/4 are experiment data and the double dot dash line *_S are simulation results.

4 DISSCUSSIONS

In this research, the tensile properties of CMT and UT-CTT materials were studied experimentally and analytically. The mean field method—Mori-Tanaka model was involved into this study as the analytical simulation model. Also the specific physical and structural properties of the DCFRTPs were investigated to perform realistic simulation.

In the results of the components and structural properties, the aspect ratio distributions of CMT measured show the different tendency (Fig. 4). The reason is considered as: to ensure the demanded impregnation condition, fiber breakage have more possibility to happen in high V_f condition. High

transverse compressive stress will occur due to the increase of molding pressure and fibers interaction during molding processes.

The CMT and UT-CTT have apparently different structures as mentioned. But both in the mat structures in CMTs and locally independent laminate structures in UT-CTTs (Fig. 6), the in-plane and out-of-plane fiber orientation are almost the same. The reason is considered because the compression molding processes, the fibers were almost entirely pressed and aligned to the in-plane direction, and in the area have higher reinforcement contact density the waviness will represent as the out-of-plane oriented fibers. Because the CMT materials are composted with the carbon fiber monofilament, which means the contact density of the reinforcement is much higher than the UT-CTT composted with tapes. This difference lead to slight difference between the fiber orientations of CMT and UT-CTT that the CMT have higher out-of-plane orientation ratio.

The comparison between the experimental and the Mori-Tanaka model simulation data give different results compare with the previous researches [6, 10]. In the previous researches, it has been shown that the Mori-Tanaka model is accurate for reinforcement V_f less than 20% to 30% and aspect ratio less than 100. When these parameter become higher, the simulation provide inaccurate estimations. However, in this study, the consequence indicated that in CMT where the aspect ratio is range from 0 to 1000 and the V_f is lower than 20%, the simulation did not deliver accurate effective properties. Furthermore, in UT-CTT where the aspect ratio have the range from 200 to 500 and the V_f is higher than 50%, the simulation give very good and accurate estimations of the tensile properties. This result indicated the feasibility to use Mori-Tanaka model in simulations for DCFRTP have high V_f and high aspect ratio.

To understand the mechanism of this result, the difference between the components and structural properties of CMT and UT-CTT were compared in details. The most apparent difference between CMT and UT-CTT is the fiber winding. From Fig. 6 that in CMT structures, winding can be found clearly from the carbon fiber monofilaments, but in the UT-CTT structure, the laminate-like structures show the straight aligned fibers. This difference is occurred due to the impregnation of resin during compression molding processes, because the CMT have higher fiber contact density which increase the impregnation difficulty, and the more intense impregnation processes lead to the fiber elastic deformation. After the curing processes, the elastic deformation in CMT will be fixed in the materials as the residual stress. Because in UT-CTT, this process rarely happen, so the mechanical performance of UT-CTT will closer to the theoretical value compare to the CMT. In addition, when the CMT is reheated, this fiber elastic deformation will release when the resin is melted and the fiber structure will be expanded. This phenomenon have been researched and called as the ‘deconsolidation’ of the material [19] (Fig. 11).

Figure 11: General CMT 1 (a), CMT 2 (b) and re-heated CMT 1 (c) and CMT 2 (d); the micrograph of CMT (e).

Moreover, in CMT materials, the experimental stress-strain curves display plastic progression before the fracture, this phenomenon is considered to be the yielding and release of the winding fiber structure

lead by the initial damages, which can also support the discussion given above.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In present research, the tensile properties of two kinds of DCFRTP—CMT and UT-CTT were studied experimentally and analytically. The Mori-Tanaka model was introduced into the analytically homogenization. The components and structural properties of the materials were measured in detail to ensure the accuracy of simulation. The estimations show different results compare with the previous researches that the Mori-Tanaka simulations have good agreement with the experimental results even in materials with high V_f and high aspect ratio, but results also have dissimilarities in different materials. The reason of the mismatch between the Mori-Tanaka estimation and experiment are considered to be occurred by the residual elastic deformation of the embedded fiber structures in the material.

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